

Chinese Composite Scale of Morningness: Psychometric Properties of the Full and the Reduced Versions and Their Relevance to Business

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Abstract

Purpose: This study translates the Composite Scale of Morningness (CSM) into Chinese and assesses its psychometric properties and cross-cultural applicability. It also proposes a reduced Chinese CSM.

Methods: Chinese students (225 females, 168 males, 393 in total) enrolled in undergraduate and graduate courses at a university in China answer the questionnaire in class. Factor analysis with the principal component extraction method is used to analyze the data.

Results: The internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = .837) of the full Chinese CSM (fcCSM) is comparable to that of the original English scale. The reduced Chinese CSM (rcCSM) consisting of Items 1, 2, 5, 8, 9, and 11 improves the fcCSM by deleting items that are redundant or have poor statistical properties. Its Cronbach's alpha is .738.

Conclusions: Because the rcCSM contains little redundancy and ambiguity, it minimizes the chance of confusing and annoying respondents and thus maximizes response accuracy. The scale is short, easy to understand, easy to use, and applicable for many purposes, such as evaluating respondents' sleep and wakefulness. Besides, a shorter scale saves a lot of time and costs in administering the questionnaires.

Keywords: Chronobiology, Circadian rhythms, Human biological rhythms, Test reliability, Psychometrics, Composite Scale of Morningness

Practitioner Summary

This research examines the validity and reliability of the Chinese-translated Composite Scale of Morningness on 393 Chinese adult students. The internal consistency is very high. The proposed 6-item scale is reliable, easy, and helpful for many purposes and should be used to maximize accuracy and respondents' willingness to respond.

When people feel sleepy, which can be relevant to time of day, they may seek more variety of choices. It was demonstrated that greater sleepiness increased consumers' variety seeking because they needed arousal to maintain wakefulness (Huang et al., 2019). In addition, it was found that the influence of time of day on variety-seeking was relevant to the pattern of circadian arousal (Gullo et al., 2019), which refers to changes in arousal levels due to biological variables that show rhythms with a cycle length of 24 hours (Minors & Waterhouse, 1985).

Another marketing study by Pornpitakpan (2004) investigated the influence of circadian arousal, endorser expertise, and argument strength of a message on attitudes toward the brand and purchase intentions. The quasi-experimental design is a 2 (high versus low endorser expertise) x 2 (strong versus weak arguments) x 2 (morning-type versus evening-type persons) x 3 (advertisement viewing time: 10 a.m., 3 p.m., or 8 p.m.) between-subjects factorial design with 602 Thai female adults. The results show that for both morning-type and evening-type persons, higher argument strength led to better attitudes toward the brand and higher purchase intentions, regardless of endorser expertise and advertisement viewing time. When morning-type persons view the advertisements in the morning and evening, the high and the low-expertise endorsers had no different effect on attitudes toward the brand, regardless of argument strength. When they viewed the advertisements in the afternoon, the high expertise endorser induced better attitudes toward the brand than did the low expertise endorser, regardless of argument strength. For evening-type persons, endorser expertise showed no effects on the two dependent variables. Clearly, circadian arousal and people's morningness-eveningness have profound implications for marketing strategies.

Extant evidence suggests a strong relationship between people's morningness-eveningness and the fundamental properties of the circadian system (Kerkhof, 1985). Morning people tend to have high circadian arousal early in the day, whereas evening ones do so later. Many paper-and-pencil instruments have been developed to measure morningness-eveningness, and the psychometric properties of these scales have been reported by the scale developers and other researchers (e.g., Pornpitakpan, 1998, 2000). Tonetti et al. (2015) reviewed the measures of circadian preference in childhood and adolescence. Adan et al. (2012) and Di Milia et al. (2013) reviewed the psychometric properties of various circadian typology measures. Specifically, Adan et al. (2012) reported some methodological limitations regarding samples, gender biases, potential common-method variance, predictive values, inter-relationships between circadian rhythm parameters, and cutoff criteria.

Most published scales of morningness were developed in English, but because not everybody in the world can understand English, there is an obvious need to create morningness scales in the language of the persons being measured. A common approach is to translate from established scales. For example, the Composite Scale of Morningness (CSM) has been widely used and has been found to possess good psychometric properties, to be stable over time (Greenwood, 1994), to have predictive validity (Guthrie et al., 1995), and to receive wide applications in studies regarding the relationship between chronotype and various personality or sleep variables (Drezno, Stolarski, & Matthews, 2019). However, as specified in Standard 13.4 of the Standards for Educational and Psychological Testing (American Educational Research Association et al., 1985), "when a test is translated from one language or dialect to another, its reliability and validity for the uses intended in the linguistic groups to be tested should be established" (p. 75). This is especially important in light of the fact that properties of morningness scales have been

shown to vary by age, culture, and so on (Caci et al., 2005; Kerkhof, 1985). To assess the cross-cultural applicability of the CSM, this research aims to investigate the psychometric properties of CSM when translated into Chinese and conducted on Chinese people. The following reviews the literature pertaining to the CSM and then presents the methods, results, and discussion.

Literature Review

The CSM has been translated into many languages and administered on participants from various countries, for example, Arabic, Argentine, Bangladeshi, Colombian, Dutch, French, German, Hindi, Italian, Korean, Persian, Peruvian, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Russian, Spanish, Thai, Turkish, and Ukrainian. Appendix 1 summarizes the psychometric properties of various language versions of the CSM. Several insights can be drawn from Appendix 1. First, in different cultures, the full CSM shows strong internal consistency and sufficient validity against other chronotype questionnaires as well as other recognized chronotype correlates such as mood (Hasan et al., 2022), physical and mental performance (Caci et al., 1999), and conscientiousness (Randler, 2009).

Second, inconsistencies exist regarding the associations between gender/age and morningness–eveningness. Generally, females report greater morningness than do males (e.g., Di Milia & Bohle, 2009), and older people tend to exhibit greater morningness than do younger people, especially university students (e.g., Gil et al., 2008). In other words, school students tend to be evening type. However, some studies did not reveal any gender/age differences in relation to circadian rhythms (e.g., Pordanjani & Ebrahimi, 2017). The discrepant findings regarding gender/age differences might be attributed to factors such as geographic location, cultural differences, and the sample size. When there is a broader range of samples, for example, in the community sample (Kato et al., 2019), the correlation between gender/age and morningness tend to emerge.

Third, although the cutoff values differ in the translated versions, the scores fall within similar range across the countries. Fourth, the factor structure differs by samples in different studies, for example, one factor, two factors, or three factors. This suggests that effective application of CSM needs to fit into specific samples and cultural backgrounds. Fifth, it is worth noting that in several studies, Item 7 (“At what time in the evening do you feel tired and as a result, in need of sleep?”) has the lowest item-total correlation, and when it is removed, the scale usually demonstrates higher reliability than when it is included (Caci et al., 1999; Di Milia & Bohle, 2009; Gil et al., 2008; Greenwood, 1994). Finally, Mandarin Chinese translations of the CSM along with verification of their psychometric properties have been very scarce.

Method

Instruments and Procedure

Appendix 2 shows the necessary modifications of the original CSM. Two scholars fluent in English and native to Chinese independently translated this modified CSM and then resolved discrepancies. The translated scale was then distributed to participants to answer in class. All the questions (i.e., the CSM and a few demographic questions) and procedures were evaluated by peers to confirm that the study was legal and met international guidelines for research on humans, especially the Declaration of Helsinki—the questions were not sensitive and caused no mental and physical harm to participants. Because the study did not receive funding from any organization, it did not need to go through any ethics committee in the country. Assured that their answers to the questionnaire would be kept confidential and used for academic research only, participants were aware that (i) they had the right to participate or to not participate in the survey, which involved anonymously answering a questionnaire

about their preferred time of doing things, and (ii) if they decided to answer the questionnaire, it indicated that they gave consent to participate in the research.

Participants

Participants are 393 Chinese students in undergraduate and graduate programs at an institution in China (225, or 57.25% women; 168, or 42.75% men). They were invited to answer the questionnaire in the class. They were in the middle and upper social classes, aged 18 to 47 ($M = 21.47$, $SD = 3.671$), and in generally good health.

Descriptive Statistics

The composite scores (i.e., the sum of all 13 items) range from 13 to 47 (the possible range is 13 to 55). Higher scores indicate higher degrees of morningness. The mean and standard deviation of the composite scores are 28.28 and 6.292, respectively, for the total sample; 28.59 and 6.639, respectively, for female participants; and 27.88 and 5.788, respectively, for male participants. The mean composite scores of males and females do not differ significantly, $t(391) = -1.117$, $p = .265$. The distribution is slightly positively skewed (skewness = .453, standard error of skewness = .123), indicating that participants are relatively evening-type. The kurtosis is $-.029$ with a standard error of .246. The 10th and 90th percentiles for classifying people into evening-type, intermediate-type, and morning-type are 20.4 and 37, respectively, for the total sample; 20 and 35, respectively, for males; and 20.6 and 38, respectively, for females. The cutoff scores between males and females are almost similar. Because the sum scores are whole numbers, given these percentiles, a person with total scores of 20 or less in this sample can be considered as evening-type, while a person with total scores of 37 or higher in this sample can be regarded as morning-type.

Results

The Full Chinese Composite Scale of Morningness (fcCSM)

Table 1 shows Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the fcCSM, the corrected item-total correlation, and alpha if the item is deleted. The alpha coefficient .837 is very high and cannot be improved by deleting any item from the scale.

Table 1

Item-Total Correlations and Reliability Estimates of the Full Chinese Composite Scale of Morningness

Item	Corrected item-total correlation	Alpha if item deleted
1	.612	.815
2	.474	.826
3	.433	.829
4	.311	.836
5	.430	.829
6	.488	.825
7	.382	.834
8	.415	.830
9	.692	.810
10	.590	.819
11	.485	.826
12	.370	.833
13	.629	.815

Alpha = .837; Standardized item alpha = .837

Factor analysis was performed to investigate the structure of the CSM and to explore which items can be eliminated to achieve a shorter scale without losing much reliability. The principal component extraction method, in which all the variance in the measured variables contributes to the solution, was used because it is suitable for empirically summarizing the data. Oblique rotation, which permits correlation between factors, was conducted. Among the various oblique rotation methods, oblimin with Kaiser normalization was used because it produced a simple structure and permitted moderate correlation between factors. Three components were extracted based on the eigenvalue-greater-than-one criterion. Table 2 displays the pattern matrix of the full scale. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy is .858, showing the appropriateness of factor analysis on the variables.

Table 2
Pattern Matrix of the Full Chinese Composite Scale of Morningness Based on Oblimin with Kaiser Normalization Rotation

Item number and brief content	Component		
	I	II	III
13: To what extent you are a morning or evening active individual	.720	.220	.045
9: Which ONE of these types do you consider yourself to be	.680	.257	.133
2: Considering your only “feeling best” rhythm, at what time would you go to bed	.592	-.255	.284
8: Considering only your own “feeling best” rhythm, which ONE of the four testing times would you choose?	.582	.077	.014
7: At what time in the evening do you feel tired and in need of sleep	.580	-.054	.042
4: How alert do you feel during the first half hour after having awakened in the morning	-.006	.809	-.014
5: During the first half hour after having awakened in the morning, how tired do you feel	.125	.587	.155
3: How easy do you find getting up in the morning	.421	.575	-.124
11: If you always had to rise at 6:00 a.m., what do you think it would be like	-.074	.061	.779
10: When would you prefer to rise if you were totally free to arrange your time	.197	-.033	.689
1: Considering only your own “feeling best” rhythm, at what time would you get up	.345	-.087	.603
6: Bearing in mind your own “feeling best” rhythm, how do you think you would perform in a physical exercise during 7:00 – 8:00 a.m.	.170	-.017	.577
12: How long does it usually take before you “recover your senses” in the morning after rising from a night’s sleep	-.262	.491	.528

Note. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy = .858. The correlation between Component I and II is .159, between I and III is .394, and between II and III is .227.

According to Comrey (1973), variables with loadings higher than .71 are considered excellent measures of the factor, .63 very good, .55 good, .45 fair, and .32 poor. Thus, only variables with loadings higher than .45 were considered in Table 2. Items 13, 9, 2, 8, and 7 load on Component I; Items 4, 5, and 3 load on Component II; and Items 11, 10, 1, 6, and 12 load on Component III.

The Reduced Chinese Composite Scale of Morningness (rcCSM)

In order to achieve a shorter CSM, items with a loading lower than or equal to .58 in Table 2 were dropped: Items 7, 3, 6, and 12. In addition, the item with a lower corrected item-total correlation (see Table 1) in the following pairs with almost identical meaning was dropped: (i) Item 10 was dropped from the pair Item 1 (.612) and Item 10 (.59), which are about getting up time; (ii) Item 4 was dropped from the pair Item 4 (.311) and Item 5 (.43), which are reversed wording of each other (feeling alert vs. feeling tired in the first half hour after getting up); and (iii) Item 13 was dropped from the pair Item 9 (.692) and Item 13 (.629), which are about self-reported morningness-eveningness. This elimination results in a reduced scale containing Items 1, 2, 5, 8, 9, and 11. Factor analysis was then performed on this reduced scale, with principal component extraction. Only one component could be extracted based on the eigenvalues-greater-than-one principle, thus no rotation. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure

of sampling adequacy is .788, a slight drop from .858 of the full scale. The alpha coefficient of this rcCSM is .738, compared with .837 of the full scale. Appendix 3 shows the fcCSM and rcCSM. This rcCSM is recommended for measuring Chinese people's morningness-eveningness.

Discussion

Summary of the Research and Its Contributions

In response to the this guideline: “when a test is translated from one language or dialect to another, its reliability and validity for the uses intended in the linguistic groups to be tested should be established” (American Educational Research Association et al., 1985, p. 75), this research translates the CSM in Smith et al. (1989) into Chinese and administers it to 393 Chinese students in China to assess its cross-cultural applicability. It then proposes a reduced Chinese CSM (rcCSM). The results show that the internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = .837) of the full Chinese CSM is comparable to that of the original English scale. The rcCSM (consisting of Items 1, 2, 5, 8, 9, and 11) retains good internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = .738).

Despite the slight reduction in Cronbach's alpha compared with that of the full scale, the rcCSM is worthwhile because of the following advantages. First, the rcCSM improves the full scale by dropping items that are redundant or have poor statistical properties. Second, because it contains very little redundancy and ambiguity, it minimizes the chance of confusing or annoying respondents and thus maximizes response accuracy. Third, the scale is short, easy to understand, and easy to administer. Finally, shortening the questionnaire can save a lot of time and costs in administering the questionnaire. Specifically, one of the factors research companies use in determining the service fees is the number of questions (i.e., the length of the questionnaires), apart from the research methodology, the number and type of respondents, the level of reporting, the turn-around time, and so forth.

As for the question of “Why a Chinese CSM is needed”, China has a huge population of 1,417 million as of February 2025 (<https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/china-population>), while about 624 million people around the world speak English as their mother tongue (<https://www.worlddata.info/languages/index.php>). It is convenient and sometimes inevitable to use Chinese questionnaires in China because many Chinese people do not understand English. Whenever researchers require a short Chinese scale with good psychometric properties to measure Chinese people's morningness, the rcCSM should serve the purpose.

Appendix 4 discusses similarities and differences between the rcCSM and the reduced morningness-eveningness questionnaire (rMEQ). In summary, the rcCSM consists of six items whereas the rMEQ consists of five items. Three items in the rcCSM are not in the rMEQ, and the other three are quite similar. The rcCSM uses an easier to understand response format and adds the meaning of morning-type and evening-type for clarity. The time in the response choices also differ between the rcCSM and rMEQ.

Potential Uses and Benefits of the rcCSM

The rcCSM may be used for many purposes, such as evaluating respondents' sleep and wakefulness and investigating the effects of respondents' circadian arousal on their attitudes, behaviors, performances, personality traits, and other variables. In particular, it should help in selecting staff for shiftwork in many professions, such as air traffic controllers, caregivers, factory workers, firefighters, flight attendants, hotel employees, nurses, physicians, pilots, prison officers, security guards, truck drivers, and so on. Evidence suggests that individuals of different circadian types adapt differently to shiftwork (Adan et al., 2012) because of their circadian rhythms and sleeping flexibility.

Results from many studies (Zion, Drach-Zahavy, & Shochat 2018) emphasize including age and chronotype in shiftwork research and scheduling. Although this study does not investigate the actual use of the rcCSM for shiftwork-staff selection, the application potential appears promising because, with its appropriate psychometric properties, the scale can differentiate between morning and evening people, and thus between those who adapt well to nightwork and shiftwork and those who do not. However, because the scale's predictive ability for adaptation/tolerance to nightwork and shiftwork was not empirically validated in this study, it should be tested in future research. Additionally, the rcCSM should be useful for academic and managerial studies that often employ lengthy questionnaires to investigate people's circadian types and many other variables.

Besides the circadian typology related to the phase, researchers are investigating the amplitude of individuals' circadian rhythmicity. For instance, Díaz-Morales et al. (2017) examined the validity of the Spanish version of the morningness–eveningness–stability scale–improved (MESSi) by considering the subjective phase and amplitude by morning affect, eveningness, and distinctness sub-scales. Results confirmed that subjective amplitude was related to, but also differentiating, morningness-eveningness. Pilz et al. (2018) examined the rhythmicity of mood symptoms in people susceptible to psychiatric disorders. Brazilian and Spanish participants completed the Self-Reporting Questionnaire-20 for non-psychotic mental disorders, the Mood Rhythm Instrument, and the Munich ChronoType Questionnaire. Results showed that the rhythmicity of specific mood-related symptoms and behaviors, especially pessimism and motivation to exercise, were associated with susceptibility to psychiatric disorders. Circadian misalignment was associated with a higher risk for mental health conditions. It is clear that such evolving research streams provide opportunities to use the rcCSM recommended in this study when the research involves Chinese participants.

Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

The scope and limitations of this study and future research suggestions are as follows. First, this study does not aim to compare the psychometric properties of the Chinese CSM scales between age groups or between sexes. Instead, because the gender distribution in the sample is not much different (57.25% females, 42.75% males) and the age range of 18–47 years is not that large, the sample is not divided into groups.

Second, this study was based on a moderate sample size of university students with slightly more females than males. This means that relevance of outcomes for work environment may be questioned, for example, the provided cutoff-points may not generalize to non-students, who are usually shifted toward eveningness. Future research may use samples of various occupations.

Third, external validity is not investigated. Future research can examine the associations between the fcCSM/rcCSM and other morningness scales, such as the MEQ and rMEQ. It can also investigate their associations with other relevant variables, such as respondents' actual workout time on their free days.

Finally, the expected benefits of the rcCSM raised in this study are tentative. Future research should examine the psychometric properties of the rcCSM with additional Chinese samples of different characteristics.

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Appendix 1

Psychometric Properties of the Composite Scale of Morningness (CSM) in Various Languages

Note: The first study in the table is the first study to propose the CSM. Later studies are arranged by English language, other foreign languages of the scale, then author name and publication year. **Only the citations mentioned in Column 1 are listed in the References section.** The table header row is not repeated on other pages to save space.

Language of the scale; author name; publication year	Sample size; sample characteristics; data collection method	Full scale: reliability; number of extracted factors; which items load on which factor; cutoff values; data analysis method	Reduced scale: reliability; number of extracted factors; which items load on which factor; cutoff values; data analysis method	Gender differences in CSM scores	Age differences in CSM scores	Evidence of validity (associations with other chronotype scales, sleep schedules, and chronotype correlates such as personality, temperament, well-being, mood, performance, mental health)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> English scale. Smith et al. (1989). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sample 1: 501 undergraduates from a large midwestern university in the USA who answered the survey items on a voluntary basis for class credit (no characteristics information available). Sample 2: 113 undergraduate students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alpha = .87 (sample 1) 3 factors, specific item loadings were not provided. 4 items load on Factor 1. 4 items load on Factor 2. 5 items load on Factor 3. Scores ≤ 22 are evening-type, $23 \leq$ scores ≤ 43 are intermediates, scores ≥ 44 are morning-type. Principal component analysis. Alpha = .83 (sample 2) No further discussion on sample 2. 	No discussion.	No discussion.	No discussion.	CSM correlated with the Horne and Östberg and the Torsvall and Akerstedt scales.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> English scale Di Milia and Bohle (2009). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sample 1: 675 undergraduate students enrolled in introductory Psychology or Organizational Behaviour at two Australian universities (245 males, 427 females, age 16–53). Sample 2: 721 Australian university students living in a small regional city (201 males, 520 females, age 17–72). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alpha = .89. Alpha = .90 (if item 7 deleted). 2 factors (not fit the data). 3 factors (not fit the data). No further discussion on item loading and cutoff values. This study replicated the two-factor structure by Smith et al. (2002) and the three-factor structure by Caci et al. (2005) 	No discussion.	Significant gender differences.	Significant age differences.	Morningness increased with age. CSM correlated with early/late preference scale of morningness (PS): Being morning-oriented was associated with earlier bed and wake times for both work-days and weekends.

	Data collection from both samples (N=1396) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test-retest sample: 235 Australian university students living in a small regional city (201 males, 520 females, age 17–72). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confirmatory factor analysis. • Alpha = .84 (test-retest reliability). No further discussion. 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • English scale. • Greenwood (1994). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 424 health science students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSM had good psychometric properties when used on samples of students and on the sample of 35 individuals working on rotating shifts. • Removing Item 7 improved the reliability. • CSM scores were found to be stable over time and did not change when subjects were exposed to night- and shiftwork. • Cutoff scores: 10th percentile = 27, 90th percentile = 44. 	No discussion.	No difference.	No information.	No information.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • English scale. • Dutch scale. • Colombian scale. • Spanish scale. • Smith et al. (2002). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1794 university students in six countries, namely, the USA, England, the Netherlands, Colombia, Spain, and India (65% females, age 18–22). • USA sample: 579 undergraduate psychology students (70.5% females, mean age 19). All data were collected in the spring semester (late winter to early spring) at various times of the day. • England sample: 183 first-year university student (60.7% females, mean age 20.3). Data were collected in the afternoon. • Netherlands sample: 283 first-year psychology students (73.1% women, mean age 21.1). Data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .90 (total sample, $n = 1794$). • Alpha = .87 (England sample, $n = 165$). • Alpha = .90 (Netherlands sample, $n = 281$). • Alpha = .81 (Spain sample, $n = 159$). • Alpha = .81 (Columbia sample, $n = 293$). • Alpha = .88 (USA sample, $n = 551$). • Alpha = .84 (India sample, $n = 300$). • 2 factors. • Items 3, 4, 5, 12 load on Factor 1. • Items 1, 2, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13 load on Factor 2. • Cutoff values are not clarified. 	No discussion.	No discussion.	No discussion.	<p>Morning and evening orientation correlated with alertness: extreme evening types reported greater alertness than extreme morning types in the evening hours, and extreme morning types reported greater alertness than extreme evening types in the morning hours.</p> <p>CSM scores correlated with preferred and normal (actual) arise and bedtimes for weekdays and weekends [only one out of 28 comparisons for each scale did not reach significance (total n and each country, based on their individual cut scores)]; evening types reported later arise and bed times and the morning types reported earlier</p>

	<p>were collected in the morning and afternoon.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colombia sample: 303 university students (65.3% females, mean age 23.6). The surveys were filled out during class sessions; three classes met in the early morning and one met at night; the remaining classes met during various times of the day. • Spain sample: 159 psychology students (79.2% females, mean age 19.9). Data were collected in the morning. • India sample: 150 undergraduate and 150 postgraduate students (39.7% females, mean age 21.8). Data were collected between morning and early afternoon. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploratory factor analysis & SIFASP analysis. 				<p>arise and bed times; the intermediate types fell between the two extremes.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arabic scale • Mansour et al. (2015). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 79 Arabic speaker participants: faculty psychiatrists at the Department of Psychiatry, Mansoura University Hospitals (MUH), Mansoura, Egypt (31 males, 48 females, age 17–62). • No details on data collection methods. 	Information not available.	Information not available.	Information not available.	Information not available.	<p>The frequency of siesta naps per week was significantly correlated with the total CSM score: the greater the number of siesta naps, the lower the CSM score, i.e., evening types taking more naps.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Argentine scale. • Gil et al. (2008). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 304 participants living in the cities of San Luis, Mendoza, and General Pico (La Pampa), Argentina answered both the CS and PS scales (30.9% males, 69.1% females, age 17–78). • No details on data collection methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .86. • Alpha = .87 (without item 7). • 3 factors. • Items 1, 3, 6, 10, 11 load on Factor 1. • Items 4, 5, 12 load on Factor 2. • Items 2, 7, 8, 9, 13 load on Factor 3. • Scores ≤ 26 are evening-type, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No discussion. 	No differences.	<p>Significant age differences: higher scores in older persons.</p>	<p>CSM correlated with PS (early/late preference scale of morningness).</p>

		<p>scores ≥ 46 are morning-type.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principal component analysis. 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bangladeshi scale • Hasan et al. (2022). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1164 Bangladeshi university students in Bangladesh (38.8% females, age 18–27): 149 participants in a classroom setting, and 1015 participants from online. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .88. • 2 factors. • Items 1, 2, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13 load on Factor 1. • Items 3, 4, 5, 12 load on Factor 2. • Scores ≤ 26 are evening-type, scores ≥ 46 are morning-type. • Exploratory factor analysis: Principal component analysis (subsample 1). • Confirmatory factor analysis (subsample 2). 	No discussion.	No differences.	No differences.	CSM scores correlated with sleep habits, wake-up times, sleep duration, mid-sleep times, social jetlag, mood, and mental health. Higher CSM score (morningness) correlated with earlier sleep times, better mood and mental health.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colombian scale. • Smith et al. (2002), see details in the English scale above as the study covered several languages. 						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dutch scale. • Smith et al. (2002), see details in the English scale above as the study covered several languages. 						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • French scale. • Caci et al. (1999). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 356 French students from five nursing schools in Nice, Cannes, and Monaco (53 males, 303 females, age 18–54). • No details on data collection methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .849. • Removing item 7 improved alpha. • 1 factor. • All items but 7 and 8 load on the factor. • Scores ≤ 30 are evening-type, $31 \leq$ scores ≤ 44 are intermediates, scores ≥ 45 are morning-type. • Factorial analysis. 	No discussions.	No differences.	No differences.	Morningness correlated with shorter sleep, early rising times and bedtimes and early peak of physical and mental performance.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • French scale. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 60 first-year nursing students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .874 (males). 	No discussion.	No differences.	No discussion.	No discussion.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caci et al. (2000). 	<p>at the University Hospital Center in Nice, France filled out the CSM in October 1997 (test time) and November 1998 (retest time) (11 males, 49 females, age 18–40.42).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .879 (males, retest). • Alpha = .897 (females). • Alpha = .904 (females, retest). • No further discussion. 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • German scale. • Randler (2008). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3745 German pupils and university students in Germany (1355 males, 2390 females, age 9–52). • No details on data collection methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .84. • 3 factors. • Items 3, 4, 5, 6, 11, 12 load on Factor 1. • Items 1, 2, 7, 9, 13 load on Factor 2. • Items 8, 10 load on Factor 3. • Scores ≤ 26 are evening-type, scores ≥ 43 are morning-type. • Principal component analysis. 	No discussion.	Significant gender differences and interaction between age and gender.	Significant age differences: CSM scores differed significantly between the age of 12 and 13, indicating the shift towards evening preferences at the age of approximately 12 years.	CSM correlated with Morningness Eveningness Questionnaire (MEQ).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • German scale. • Randler (2009) (Part I). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sample 1: 300 university students in Germany (116 males, 183 females, 1 sex not specified, age 18–49). • Sample 2: 488 university students in Germany (207 men, 281 women, age 20–49). • Sample 3: 491 pupils in Germany (251 males, 240 females, age 13–18) & 488 students (207 males, 281 females). • No details on data collection methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .846. • No further discussion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .722 (for student and pupil samples used for validation of full scale). • 2 factors. • Items 1, 2, 9, 10 load on Factor 1. • Items 5, 6, 12 load on Factor 2. • Cutoff scores are not mentioned. • Principal component analysis. 	No discussion.	No discussion.	Full CSM scores correlated with physical and cognitive peak performance, sleep–wake rhythm, and midpoint of sleep.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • German scale. • Randler (2009) (Part II). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sample 1: 206 university students in Germany (34 males, 172 females, age 20–42) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See the information in the above cell. 	First validation of the rCSM (with sleep–wake rhythm)	No discussion.	No discussion.	Reduced CSM scores correlated with sleep–wake rhythm (no correlation with rise times on

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sample 2: 274 adolescents in Germany (132 males, 142 females, age 10–18). • The above 2 samples are for the first and second validation. • Sample 3: 79 university students in Germany (12 males, 67 females, age 19–30). • The above sample 3 is for the third and fourth validation. • University names and dates were given, no details about collection methods. • Sample for test-retest: 46 university students in Germany (9 males, 37 females, age 19–30). 		<p>and midpoint of sleep)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .819 (sample 1). • Alpha = .637 (sample 2). <p>Second validation (with personality): No further discussion.</p> <p>Third validation (with MEQ): No discussion.</p> <p>Fourth validation (with subjective alertness ratings): No discussion.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test-retest reliability alpha = .88. 			<p>weekdays); midpoint of sleep; conscientiousness; morningness eveningness questionnaire (MEQ); subjective alertness.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hindi scale. • Bhatia et al. (2013). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sample 1: 130 Indian students who are bilingual in Hindi and English (47 high school students in grade 9 in the Delhi region, 83 female first-year nursing postgraduate students in New Delhi). • Sample 2: Participants completed the Hindi version alone (104 young adults following a door-to-door survey of a local, community, 160 middle aged adults attending free Yoga classes in a Government run Yoga institute). • No details on data collection methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .854. • 2 factors. • Items 1, 2, 7, 9, 10, 11 load on Factor 1. • Items 3, 4, 5, 12 load on Factor 2. • Scores ≤ 36 are evening-type, $36 < \text{scores} < 49$ are intermediates, scores ≥ 49 are morning-type. • Principal component analysis. 	<p>No discussion.</p>	<p>No differences.</p>	<p>Significant age differences: school students are more likely to be evening type.</p>	<p>No discussion.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Italian scale. • Natale and Alzani (2001). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 89 university students (23 males, 66 females, age 22–28) participated in a laboratory experiment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scores ≤ 26 are evening-type, scores ≥ 42 are morning-type. • No further discussion. 	<p>No discussion.</p>	<p>Significant gender differences: a higher percentage of morning-type subjects among females and a higher percentage of evening-type among males.</p>	<p>No discussion.</p>	<p>Time of day correlated with body temperature: the time of day when body temperature curve reached the minimum value was the same (8 a.m.) for all the 3 typologies. Morningness correlated with subjective alertness: the closer to the morning type, the higher the levels of subjective alertness were at 8 a.m. and 2 p.m., whereas the exact contrary happened at 11 p.m. CSM scores correlated with mood levels at 8 a.m.: the higher the CSM score was (i.e., the more we get near to the morning type) the higher the levels of subjective mood were at 8 a.m. The subjective alertness trends correlated with the mood trend.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Japanese scale • Kato et al. (2019). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sample 1: 348 Japanese university students completed the CSM before or after class (196 males, 152 females, mean age = 19.54 years, SD = 1.92). • Sample 2: 170 residents attending a community public health center for their annual health check (50 males, 120 females, mean age = 52.19 years, SD = 12.23). • No details on data collection methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .82. • 2 factors. • Items 1, 2, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13 load on Factor 1. • Items 3, 4, 5, 12 load on Factor 2. • Item 6 does not load on any factor. • Scores ≤ 27 are evening-type, scores ≥ 45 are morning-type. • Confirmatory factor analysis. 	<p>No discussion.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No differences in the university sample. • Significant gender differences in the total sample and the community sample. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No differences in the university sample. • Significant age differences in the community sample. 	<p>Morningness correlated with sleep midpoints during free and working days.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Korean scale • Kim and Lee (2021). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 472 patients diagnosed with the Mini-International Neuropsychiatric Interview were recruited as part of the Mood Disorder Cohort Research Consortium study from nine sites in Korea (including 167 	<p>No discussion.</p>	<p>No discussion.</p>	<p>No discussion.</p>	<p>No discussion.</p>	<p>CSM negatively correlated with sleep time during weekdays and weekends, with wake time during weekdays and weekends, and with sleep latency (i.e., morningness correlated with sleeping and waking earlier during both</p>

	<p>patients with major depression disorders, i.e., MDD, 133 patients with bipolar disorder I, i.e., BD I, 172 patients with bipolar disorder II, i.e., BD II, 265 females, mean age 23.013, SD = 3.398).</p> <p>• Test–retest sample: 366 participants completed the CSM again at an interval of 12 weeks.</p>					<p>weekdays and weekends and falling asleep faster).</p> <p>CSM positively correlated with quality of life: morningness correlated with higher self-reported quality of life.</p> <p>CSM negatively correlated with impulsivity: morningness correlated with lower impulsivity level.</p> <p>CSM negatively correlated with depressive symptoms: morningness correlated with lower depressive symptoms.</p> <p>CSM negatively correlated with hypomanic symptoms in bipolar patients as a group: eveningness correlated with hypomanic symptoms only with symptoms in BD II patients but not in BD I patients; BD II patients were more evening-oriented than were the BD I patients.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persian scale. • Pordanjani and Ebrahimi (2017). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 288 students were selected from all undergraduate students enrolled at the University of Bojnord, Iran (n = 3008) in the 2016-17 academic year between May and June, using the stratified random sampling method by field of study (151 males, 137 females, age 18–24). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .790. • 2 factors. • Items 1, 2, 7, 8, 9, 10, 13 load on Factor 1. • Items 3, 4, 5, 6, 11, 12 load on Factor 1. • Scores ≤ 25 are evening-type, scores ≥ 42 are morning-type. • Principal component analysis. 	No discussion.	No differences.	No differences.	<p>Strong correlations between the CSM scores and its factors of “self-assessment/activity planning” and “morning affect” with morningness eveningness questionnaire (MEQ).</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peruvian scale. • Díaz-Morales and Sánchez-López (2005). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 139 Peruvian undergraduates in Peru completed the scales during the students’ normal classes. Some groups were assessed in the morning and others in the afternoon (30 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha information not available. • Scores ≤ 25 are evening-type, scores ≥ 42 are morning-type. • No further discussion. 	No discussion.	No differences.	No discussion.	<p>CSM correlated with early/late preferences scale (PS).</p> <p>Morningness correlated with perceived level of arousal (“feeling most active”) and “feeling at one’s best”.</p>

	males, 109 females, age 18–29).					Morningness correlated with actual rising and retiring times on weekdays and weekends. Morningness correlated with perceived levels of alertness.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Polish scale. Jankowski (2015). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 952 Polish residents were tested before classes and the worker group was tested individually (62.6% females, age 13–46; 265 secondary school students, age 13–15; 150 high school students, age 16–18; 404 university students, age 19–23; 133 workers, age 24–46). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alpha = .835. 2 factors. Items 3, 4, 5, 6, 11, 12 load on Factor 1. Items 1, 2, 7, 8, 9, 10, 13 load on Factor 2. Scores ≤ 24 are evening-type, scores ≥ 43 are morning-type. Principal component analysis. 	No discussion.	No differences.	Significant age differences: eveningness was greatest in participants aged 16–18 years, and a shift toward eveningness during puberty and a shift back toward morningness in older age.	Morningness correlated with mid sleep on free days (MSF): greater morningness preferences were associated with earlier MSF from the Munich chronotype questionnaire (MCTQ).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Portuguese scale. Buekenhout et al. (2019). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 522 participants (55% females, age 65–95). No other characteristics and data collection method were given. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alpha = .81. No further details were provided. 	No discussion.	No differences.	No differences.	CSM scores correlated with sleep schedule variables: higher morningness scores were associated with earlier sleep-wake schedules. CSM scores correlated with mean sleep point on free days–sleep corrected (MSFsc).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Romanian scale. Voinescu et al. (2010) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 205 Romanian undergraduate students and adults recruited from their acquaintances as well as from people presenting to their general practitioner in Baia Mare, Romania (65.4% females, age 18–69). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alpha = .875. 2 factors. Items 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 11, 12 load on Factor 1. Items 1, 2, 7, 9, 13 load on Factor 2. Scores ≤ 27 are evening-type, 28 \leq scores ≤ 45 are intermediates, scores ≥ 46 are morning-type. Principal component analysis. 	No discussion.	Significant gender differences: men score significantly higher than do women.	Significant age differences: total scores get higher with the age.	No discussion.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Russian scale Kolomeichuk et al. 	406 Russian high school and university students in Russia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alpha = .823. 2 factors (based on an 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Four morning affect items (items 3, 	No discussion.	No discussion.	Morningness correlated with midpoint of sleep: medium

<p>(2015).</p>	<p>(129 males, 262 females, and 15 without, age 12–38). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No details on data collection methods. </p>	<p>extraction of two factors following a parallel analysis). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Items 3, 4, 5, 6, 11, 12 load on Factor 1. Items 1, 2, 7, 8, 9, 10, 13 load on Factor 2. Principal component analysis. 3 factors (based on the eigenvalue greater than one criterion). Items 3, 4, 5, 6, 12 load on Factor 1. Items 2, 7, 8, 9, 13 load on Factor 2. Items 1, 10, 11 load on Factor 3. Principal component analysis. Scores ≤ 23 are evening-type, scores ≥ 40 are morning-type. </p>	<p>4, 5, and 12). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No further discussion on a reduced scale. </p>			<p>correlation between CSM scores and wake/bed times on free days, and a medium correlation between CSM and midpoint of sleep (MS). The correlations were higher on free days.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spanish scale. Adan et al. (2005). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 391 voluntary and unpaid psychology students completed the CSM in a morning session of a Psychology course at the University of Barcelona between September and December (132 males, 259 females, age 17–33). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alpha = .87. 3 factors. Items 2, 7 load on Factor 1. Items 8, 9, 13 load on Factor 2. Items 3, 4, 5, 6, 10, 11, 12 load on Factor 3. Item 1 loads on Factor 1 in the male group only. Scores ≤ 22 are evening-type, scores ≥ 39 are morning-type. Exploratory factor analysis. 	<p>No discussion.</p>	<p>No differences.</p>	<p>No differences.</p>	<p>No discussion.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spanish scale. Díaz Morales and Sánchez-López (2004). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 329 participants in Spain recruited using a “snowball” technique, in which a group of psychology undergraduates from the Complutense University of Madrid administered the test to two people from their circle of friends, with some restrictions in order to maintain a balance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alpha = .85 (student sample, $n = 201$). Alpha = .79 (adult sample, $n = 123$). 2 factors. Items 4, 5, 12 load on Factor 2. Scores ≤ 21 are evening-type, scores ≥ 37 are morning-type (for the university sample). Scores ≤ 28 are evening-type, 	<p>No discussion.</p>	<p>No differences.</p>	<p>Significant age differences: undergraduates showed a greater tendency of eveningness.</p>	<p>No discussion.</p>

	<p>of sex and age distribution (203 young undergraduates and 126 adults, 82 males, 247 females, age 19–62).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Both samples completed the composite scale of morningness and the early/late preferences scale, along with other personality tests, in 1-hour morning and afternoon sessions during March and April. 	<p>scores ≥ 42 are morning-type (for the adult sample).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Confirmatory factor analysis. 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spanish scale. Smith et al. (2002), see details in the English scale above as the study covered several languages. 						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thai scale. Pornpitakpan (1998). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 321 Thai university students enrolled in courses at the Faculty of Arts of a university in Bangkok, Thailand answered questionnaires in class (31 males, 290 females, age 17–20). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alpha = .79. 3 factors. Items 1, 3, 10, 11 load on Factor 1. Items 4, 5, 12 load on Factor 2. Items 2, 8, 9, 13 load on Factor 3. Items 6, 7 were dropped. Scores ≤ 28 are evening-type, scores ≥ 42.8 are morning-type Principal component analysis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alpha = .70. 2 factors. Items 2, 8, 10, 11 load on Factor 1. Items 5, 9, 12 load on Factor 2. No cutoff values were suggested. Principal component analysis. 	No differences.	No discussion.	No discussion.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Turkish scale. Önder et al. (2013). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 543 high school students (51.6% males, 48.4% females, age 15–18) and 650 university students (46.2% males, 52.6% females, 8 missing data, age 19–30). Test-retest sample: 30 high school students and 40 university students. External validation sample: 93 high school students and 200 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alpha = .73 (high school sample). Alpha = .80 (university sample). 3 factors. Items 3, 4, 5, 12 load on Factor 1. Items 1, 6, 10, 11 load on Factor 2. Items 2, 7, 8, 9, 13 load on Factor 3. Scores ≤ 26 are evening-type, scores ≥ 41 are morning-type in 	No discussion.	No differences.	No discussion.	Morningness correlated with morningness eveningness questionnaire (MEQ) scores, sleep length, midpoint of sleep, rising and retiring time.

	<p>university students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No details on data collection methods. 	<p>high school sample.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scores ≤ 26 are evening-type, scores ≥ 42 are morning-type in university sample. • Principal component analysis. • Confirmatory factor analysis. <p>Test-retest reliability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .89 (high school sample). • Alpha = .84 (university sample). 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ukrainian scale. • Senyk et al. (2022). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 63 university students in Ukraine were interviewed for a pilot study. • 776 Ukrainians (24% males) living in different regions of Ukraine (n = 750) and abroad (n = 26), age 15–65. • No details on data collection methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alpha = .874. • 1 factor. • Item loadings are not mentioned. • Scores ≤ 22 are evening-type, 23 \leq scores ≤ 42 are intermediates, scores ≥ 43 are morning-type. • Confirmatory factor analysis. 	No discussion.	No differences.	No differences.	<p>Morningness correlated with consumption of stimulants: morning types consumed fewer cigarettes and less wine.</p> <p>Morningness correlated with earlier midsleep on sleep-corrected free days.</p>

Appendix 2

Modifications of the Original Composite Scale of Morningness

Pretests indicated that some participants did not understand the meaning of “morning” and “evening” persons. In addition, the time slots given in the original scale were not inclusive of the time they got up or went to bed, and the time in some choices of Items 1, 2, 7, 10 overlapped with each other. Therefore, it was necessary to modify some items as follows:

Item 1: The first choice “5:00-6:30 a.m.” is changed to “before 6:30 a.m.” and the last choice “11:00 a.m.-12:00 (noon)” is changed to “after 11:00 a.m.” In addition, the time in the third and the fourth choices are revised to be mutually exclusive.

Items 2 and 7: The first choice “8:00-9:00 p.m.” is changed to “before 9:00 p.m.” and the last choice “1:45-3:00 a.m.” is changed to “after 1:45 a.m.” In addition, the time in the third and the fourth choices are revised to be mutually exclusive.

Item 9: A brief description of morning and evening people is added to facilitate understanding. The modified item reads, “Some people get up early and are wide awake fast but go to bed early (morning type). Some need some time before they are wide awake in the morning but like to go to bed late at night (evening type). Which ONE of these types do you consider yourself to be?”

Item 10: The last choice “8:30 a.m. or later” is changed to “After 8:30 a.m.” In addition, the time in the second and the third choices are revised to be mutually exclusive.

These changes were minor and did not alter any substantive meaning of the original scale.

Appendix 3

The Full Chinese Composite Scale of Morningness (fcCSM, All Items) and the Reduced Chinese Composite Scale of Morningness (rcCSM, Only Items 1, 2, 5, 8, 9, 11)

Scoring is indicated in parentheses in front of each answer. Higher number indicates greater degree of morningness.

請為每個問題選出最能表達您的答案。

1. 請僅思考你認為自己“感覺最棒”的節奏，如果你完全可以自由安排你一天的時間，你會何時起床？

- [5] 早晨 06:30 以前
- [4] 早晨 06:30–07:45
- [3] 早晨 07:46–09:45
- [2] 上午 09:46–11:00
- [1] 上午 11:00 以後

2. 請僅思考你自己“感覺最棒”的節奏，如果你完全可以自由安排你一天的時間，你會何時上床睡覺？

- [5] 晚上 09:00 以前
- [4] 晚上 09:00–10:15
- [3] 晚上 10:16–凌晨 00:30
- [2] 凌晨 00:31–01:45
- [1] 凌晨 01:45 以後

3. 正常情況下，你覺得早上起床有多容易？

- [1] 一點也不容易
- [2] 有點容易
- [3] 相當容易
- [4] 非常容易

4. 早晨醒來後前半個小時你感覺有多清醒？

- [1] 一點也不清醒
- [2] 有點清醒
- [3] 相當清醒
- [4] 非常清醒

5. 早晨醒來後的半個小時你感覺有多疲憊？

- [1] 非常疲憊
- [2] 相當疲憊
- [3] 相當精神
- [4] 非常精神

6. 你決定開始參與一些體育運動。朋友建議你每週運動兩次，每次一小時。最適合的時間是早上 07:00–08:00。不要考慮其它，只考慮你自己“感覺最棒”的節奏，你覺得你的表現會怎麼樣？

- [4] 會表現得很好
- [3] 會表現得合理
- [2] 會覺得困難
- [1] 會覺得非常困難

7. 晚上何時你覺得疲憊，然後想睡覺？

- [5] 晚上 09:00 以前
- [4] 晚上 09:00–10:15
- [3] 晚上 10:16–凌晨 00:30
- [2] 凌晨 00:31–01:45
- [1] 凌晨 01:45 以後

8. 你希望能在某個測試中有最佳表現，你知道該測試將持續兩小時，並且會消耗你的精神。如果你可以自由安排你當天的時間。請只考慮你“感覺最棒”的節奏，你會在以下四個測試時間段中選擇哪一個？

- [4] 上午 08:00–10:00
- [3] 上午 11:00–下午 01:00
- [2] 下午 03:00–05:00
- [1] 晚上 07:00–09:00

9. 有人起床很早而且很快完全清醒，但是很早就上床睡覺（早晨型）。有些人在早晨要花些時間才能完全清醒，但是喜歡晚上很晚才上床睡覺（夜晚型）。你覺得自己屬於哪一類型呢？

- [4] 確定是早晨型
- [3] 更偏向早晨型而不是夜晚型
- [2] 更偏向夜晚型而不是早晨型
- [1] 確定是夜晚型

10. 如果你可以自由安排時間，你喜歡何時起床（假設你一天要工作 8 小時）？

- [4] 早晨 06:30 以前
- [3] 早晨 06:30–07:30
- [2] 早晨 07:31–08:30
- [1] 早晨 08:30 以後

11. 如果你每天都要早晨 06:00 起床，你覺得會是什麼情況？

- [1] 非常難受不開心
- [2] 有點困難及不開心
- [3] 不開心但不是大問題
- [4] 沒有不開心

12. 早上起來，你需要多久時間才能恢復正常狀態？

- [4] 0–10 分鐘
- [3] 11–20 分鐘
- [2] 21–40 分鐘
- [1] 超過 40 分鐘

13. 你覺得自己早上活躍還是晚上活躍？

- [4] 明顯早上活躍 (早晨清醒，夜晚疲倦)
- [3] 偏向早晨活躍
- [2] 偏向夜晚活躍
- [1] 明顯夜晚活躍 (早晨疲倦，夜晚清醒)

Appendix 4

Similarities and Differences Between the Reduced Chinese Composite Scale of Morningness (rcCSM) and the Reduced Morningness-Eveningness Questionnaire (rMEQ)

The English version of the rcCSM in this research (so that international readers can understand the meaning of each question) consists of the following items. **Take note of the remarks in the angle brackets < >.** In summary, the rcCSM consists of six items whereas the rMEQ (Adan & Almirall, 1991) consists of five items. Three items in the rcCSM are not in the rMEQ, and the other three are quite similar. The rcCSM uses an easier to understand response format and adds the meaning of morning-type and evening-type for clarity. The time in the response choices also differ between the rcCSM and rMEQ.

1. Considering only your own “feeling best” rhythm, at what time would you get up if you were entirely free to plan your day?

<This item is similar to Item 1 in the rMEQ but the response format in the rcCSM is easier to understand.>

- [5] Before 6:30 a.m.
- [4] 6:30 – 7:45 a.m.
- [3] 7:46 – 9:45 a.m.
- [2] 9:46 – 11:00 a.m.
- [1] After 11:00 a.m.

2. Considering your only “feeling best” rhythm, at what time would you go to bed if you were entirely free to plan your evening?

<This item is not in the rMEQ. Although Item 3 in the rMEQ asks about time to go to bed, the wording of the whole question is very different. In addition, the response format in the rcCSM is easier to understand.>

- [5] Before 9:00 p.m.
- [4] 9:00 p.m. – 10:15 p.m.
- [3] 10:16 p.m. – 12:30 a.m.
- [2] 12:31 a.m. – 1:45 a.m.
- [1] After 1:45 a.m.

5. During the first half hour after having awakened in the morning, how tired do you feel?

<This item is similar to Item 2 in the rMEQ except for the word “awakened” here versus “woken” in the rMEQ.>

- [1] Very tired
- [2] Fairly tired
- [3] Fairly refreshed
- [4] Very refreshed

8. You wish to be at your peak performance for a test which you know is going to be mentally exhausting and lasting for two hours. You are entirely free to plan your day, and considering only your own “feeling best” rhythm, which ONE of the four testing times would you choose?

<This item is not in the rMEQ.>

- [4] 8:00 a.m. – 10:00 a.m.
- [3] 11:00 a.m. – 1:00 p.m.
- [2] 3:00 p.m. – 5:00 p.m.
- [1] 7:00 p.m. – 9:00 p.m.

9. Some people get up early and are wide awake fast but go to bed early (morning type). Some need some time before they are wide awake in the morning but like to go to bed late at night (evening type). Which ONE of these types do you consider yourself to be?

<This item is quite similar to Item 5 in the rMEQ. Furthermore, the rcCSM adds a brief description of morning and evening people for clarity.>

- [4] Definitely a morning type
- [3] More a morning than an evening type
- [2] More an evening than a morning type
- [1] Definitely an evening type

11. If you always had to rise at 6:00 a.m., what do you think it would be like?

<This item is not in the rMEQ.>

- [1] Very difficult and unpleasant
- [2] Rather difficult and unpleasant
- [3] A little unpleasant but no great problem
- [4] Easy and not unpleasant